

Effect of ion-pairing on the kinetics of redox systems with concentrated supporting electrolyte

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Abstract

The electron-transfer reaction is of pivotal importance not only in electrochemistry, but also in other scientific disciplines, such as catalysis, biochemistry and biology. The kinetics of such reactions has been thoroughly investigated under ideal conditions (Butler and Volmer or Marcus theories) considering the Frumkin effects; however, the electron-transfer in concentrated electrolytes still lacks a general theory. Here we discuss the effect of the concentration of the supporting electrolyte (an inert salt) on the kinetics of three redox couples with different nominal charge: hexaammineruthenium, ferricyanide and ferrocene methanol. The redox couples are diluted but the supporting electrolyte concentration is high enough that significant deviations of the formal electrode potential from the ideality are observed; the kinetics is also altered. We propose a model in which the electrostatic interactions are described as a complexation between the redox active species and the counter-ions of the supporting electrolyte, in analogy with the treatment of the ion pairs. The model correctly fits the dependence of the formal potential and of the charge transfer resistance on the concentration, thus suggesting that the ion-transfer accompanying an electron-transfer plays a significant role in the overall reaction kinetics. This finding enables a more realistic description of the complex electron-transfer reactions occurring e.g., in electrocatalysis and catalysis, bioelectrochemistry and biochemistry, and electrochemical energy storage.

Keywords: Ion Pairing, electron transfer rate, complexation potential, supporting electrolyte

1. Introduction

The electron-transfer reaction is not only of fundamental importance in different fields of electrochemistry^{1,2} such as electro-catalysis^{3,4}, redox batteries⁵, and bio-electrochemistry⁶, but also in heterogeneous and homogeneous catalysis⁷, biochemistry⁸ and biology.⁹ For this reason, understanding how this process works under non-ideal, real-life conditions, such as in presence of highly concentrated salt, is of paramount importance. A model system for studying this phenomenon is constituted by the electron transfer between a redox couple in solution and an inert electrode. Redox couples are generally considered to be particularly simple systems that behave ideally¹⁰, therefore they are routinely used as experimental test to validate thermodynamic and kinetic theories. Typically a supporting electrolyte (an inert salt) is added to the solution together with the redox couple in order to increase the conductivity of the solution.^{10,11} The concentration of the supporting electrolyte is typically high enough to significantly violate the ideality.

The effects of highly concentrated electrolyte on the thermodynamics are well assessed. At relatively low concentration, Debye-Hückel theory¹² provides an evaluation of electrostatic interactions on the chemical potentials. At moderate concentrations (roughly, more than 0.1 M), more accurate (but partially empirical) theories such as the Pitzer¹³, TCPC¹⁴ and other models can be used. However at high ionic concentrations these models tend to fail due to a number of assumptions.¹⁵ Experiments have suggested for ferro/ferricyanide, ferrocene/ferrocenium, and iridium chloride¹⁶ the formation of ion pairs. It has been argued that the ion pairing mainly acts as a complexation of the most charged species, leading to a decrease of its chemical potential. Computational studies on ferrocene/ferrocenium¹⁷ and ferro/ferricyanide¹⁸ redox couples confirmed this hypothesis.

The supporting electrolyte also has an effect on the kinetics of the electron transfer, as it was observed for ferro/ferricyanide^{11,19,20} and vanadium ions.²¹ Some *ad-hoc* explanations have been suggested, among which the formation / dissolution of passivation layers, but they only work for specific cases. A summary of available literature, on the effects of supporting electrolyte concentration on thermodynamics and kinetics, is given in section S1 of the Supporting

Information (SI). The contribution of Frumkin effect is one of the most studied.²² It satisfactorily describes the behavior of the system in dilute supporting electrolytes²³ (<0.1 M) and repulsive conditions, i.e., with a positively charged redox couple at an electrode potential higher than the potential of zero charge and *vice-versa*. However, experiments conducted under attractive conditions display noticeable deviations from predictions based on the Frumkin effect, leading to results that are not thoroughly understood. For example, when the reduction of Cr^{3+} is carried out at a potential lower than the potential of zero charge, the reaction rate aligns with the Frumkin effect predictions by decreasing as salt concentration increases, but only up to a concentration of about 0.5 M. Beyond this concentration, the reaction rate exhibits a contrasting behavior.²⁴

At variance with the thermodynamics, a general kinetics treatment is still unavailable for non-ideal cases. The thorough works carried on up to now, e.g. Ref. [18, 23], analyzed the behaviour of highly concentrated electrolytes and highlighted the effect of ion-pairing; this notwithstanding, such effects are still often neglected, due to the difficulty of unambiguously identifying them among the various other concentration-related effects. In order to clarify the role of ion pairing in the behavior of the kinetic constant of the electron transfer reaction in redox couples at higher electrolyte concentrations, we studied three well-known systems: hexaammineruthenium II/III, ferro/ferricyanide, and ferrocene/ferrocenium methanol. The choice of these three redox couples was made considering that they have very different nominal charges and standard potentials, thus allowing us to cover relatively broad conditions. In particular, the hexaammineruthenium has been chosen among these redox couples because it is typically considered as a textbook ideal system. Dynamic multi-frequency analysis (DMFA) was used to obtain thermodynamic and kinetic information on the redox couples, as explained below. This *operando* technique allows the simultaneous acquisition of information on the formal redox potential and the reaction rate with high precision in a single experiment, as shown below. Moreover, if desired, DMFA allows working with one single form of the redox couple (reduced or oxidized), thus giving more flexibility in choosing the available systems to investigate.

We show that the trend of the effect of the supporting electrolyte on formal potential depends on the charge of the redox couple, while the kinetic rate constant increases with increasing

concentration, independent of the charge. We provide a general interpretation of the phenomenological thermodynamic and kinetic observation in terms of complexation, considering that the electron transfer reaction can occur not only between free redox species, but also between complexed ones.

2. Experimental Procedures

2.1 Chemicals and Solutions

The studied solutions contained one of the chemical species of the redox couple, either the oxidized or the reduced species: hexaammineruthinium II chloride, potassium hexacyanoferrate III, and ferrocene methanol. The choice of the oxidized or reduced species was done in order to maximize the stability of the solution. Potassium chloride was the choice for supporting electrolyte. All chemicals were analytical grade purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and were used as received without any further purification. The concentration of redox couples was 5 mmol L^{-1} while that of KCl ranged from 0.3 to 3 M. Measurements were conducted by fixing the concentration of the redox active species while varying the concentration of supporting electrolyte. Solutions were prepared immediately prior to taking measurements using ionized water as the solvent.

2.2 Procedures

Experiments were carried out in a three-electrode cell using a $25 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ platinum microelectrode (Pt) as the working electrode, a platinum mesh (Labor Platina) as the counter electrode and Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl) as the reference electrode (RE). Experiments with hexaammineruthinium II chloride and ferrocene methanol redox active species were carried out at $5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ with the intention of slowing down the reaction kinetics, while that of potassium hexacyanoferrate III was carried out at room temperature. The measurements were carried out in a three-electrode cell configuration. In real-world conditions, any RE is polarizable to a certain extent, and the current flowing through it causes high-frequency distortions.²⁵ This artefact was removed by introducing a 100 nF capacitor bridge.^{26,27} Reported advantages of the three-cell geometry include; reproducibility, minimization of the current line distribution, insensitivity to the position of the reference electrode. The

methodology for our electrochemical analysis leans on dynamic multi-frequency analysis (DMFA). We employed a Bio-Logic SP300 Potentiostat for this purpose, which was integrated with a 4262 PicoScope (Pico technology) two-channel oscilloscope and a two-channel 33512b waveform generator from Keysight. To generate the desired potential profile for the multi-sine signal, we utilized MATLAB scripts (version 2016b from Math Works Inc.), with the procedure detailed in ref.²⁸ Data fitting was executed in accordance with the method outlined in ref.²⁹

3. Results and Discussions

3.1 Dynamic Multifrequency Analysis: Cyclic Voltammetry and Impedance Spectra

The electron-transfer reaction was investigated during the application of a cyclic sweep of potential to the micro-electrode. Simultaneously, dynamic multi-frequency analysis (DMFA) enabled the measurement of dynamic impedance spectra²⁸ (see details on theory of DMFA in S2 of SI). At variance with usual cyclic voltammetry, in which the potential sweep follows a triangular wave, we apply a slightly smoothed wave, in which the potential changes smoothly at the reversal points (quasi-cyclic voltammetry), in order to decrease the amplitude of high-frequency components in the Fourier space. With DMFA, multiple sinusoidal perturbations are added to the quasi-triangular wave of the quasi-cyclic voltammetry and the response to these perturbations is recorded at the same time. Thus, both the response of the system to the quasi-cyclic voltammetry and the dynamic impedance spectra are acquired simultaneously with high accuracy. The workflow sequence for this study can be found in Section S3 of the SI. The impedance spectra, extracted as explained in refs.³⁰⁻³³, can be interpreted and fitted with the classic equivalent circuits^{29,34}, and therefore can be used to obtain information on the reaction's kinetics. Various concentrations of KCl as supporting electrolyte were studied.

Fig. 1 shows the set of information that can be extracted with DMFA in a single experiment. In particular, in Fig. 1a the response of the system to the quasi-cyclic voltammetry is shown. Moreover, a baseline correction, based on the mean current from DMFA, has been applied to the cyclic voltammogram in Fig 1(a). The curve has a sigmoidal shape, where the values of the current reached at the extreme of the curve are dictated by the diffusion of the redox species. It is worth

noting that only one of the two redox species (reduced or oxidized) is present in the electrolyte, therefore the curve should reach close to 0 in one of the two extremes.¹⁶ In Fig. 1b it is possible to observe the extracted impedance spectra at various electrode potentials and their fitting curves. Here we show only three for convenience, but more than 50 impedance spectra are extracted for each experiment. We fitted the impedance spectra with a Randles circuit (shown in S4 of SI) using the standard deviation of the admittance obtained according to our previous publication.³⁵

In Figs. 1c and 1d, we show the results of the charge transfer resistance R_{ct} and of the mass transport coefficient σ_{ct} as a function of the electrode potential, during both positive and negative scan. The mass transport coefficient, σ_{ct} , characterizes the rate at which species are transported to/and from the electrode surface, a crucial parameter in understanding the kinetics of electrochemical processes. This coefficient provides insights into how effectively the system facilitates the movement of species in an electrochemical system. While Fig. 1 specifically highlights the $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-/4-}$ redox couple in 3 M KCl, these findings are representative and align closely with results observed for other redox couples at different supporting electrolyte concentrations as detailed in S5 in SI. It is worth noting that the presence of the multi-sine signal used for the acquisition of the dynamic impedance spectra does not influence the response of the system to the quasi-cyclic voltammetry as demonstrated in section S6 of SI.

3.2 Dependence of the inflection point potential on the supporting electrolyte concentration

Fig. 1a shows the sigmoidal dependence of the current on the potential; the inflection point potential, E_{ip} , precisely marks the transition between the two plateaux. The value of E_{ip} is closely related to the formal electrode potential of the redox couple E_f , which is, in this case, the equilibrium potential of a solution with equal concentration of reduced and oxidized species, at the given supporting electrolyte concentration (see proof in section S7 of SI). In particular, a simple relation between E_{ip} and E_f can be obtained when: (i) the experiments are performed at slow scan rate; (ii) the system is close to the stationary state; and (iii) the redox couple is transported solely by diffusion. In Fig. 1a, the small discrepancy between the positive and the negative potential sweep is due to the weakly non-stationary condition. In order to get rid of this effect, we average

the value of the inflection point obtained during the scans in the two directions. Under these circumstances, the following relation between E_{ip} and E_f holds:

$$E_f = E_{ip} - \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \left(\frac{D_{red}}{D_{ox}} \right) \quad (1)$$

where D_{red} and D_{ox} are the diffusion coefficient of the reduced and oxidized form of the redox species. Using a microelectrode with a moderate scan rate, we achieve near quasi steady-state conditions, further validating Eq 1. This is evident from the cyclic voltammetry data in Fig. 1, where positive and negative scans have minimal horizontal displacements, around 10 mV, as seen in Fig. 1a, Fig. S3(a), and Fig. S4(a). The mean inflexion points from both scans show even smaller voltage displacements, allowing accurate evaluation despite quasi steady-state conditions. Additionally, the diffusion coefficients for the reduced and oxidized species, shown in Fig S6 of the SI, Notably, the ratios derived are proximate to unity, further reinforce our approach. The calculation of E_{ip} and of its standard deviation is discussed in section S8 of the SI. The calculation of the diffusion coefficients D_{red} and D_{ox} from the Warburg coefficient, σ_{ct} , necessary for calculating E_f , is discussed in S9 of the SI.

Fig. 2 reports the measured values of E_f as a function of the concentration of the supporting electrolyte in solution, c_S . No dependence is expected in ideal solutions; instead, there is an approximately logarithmic dependence of E_f on the supporting electrolyte concentration. The direction of the shift is dependent on the charge carried by the active species. The negatively charged $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-/4-}$ redox couple exhibit a shift towards the positive direction, while the positively charged couples, i.e. $[\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_6]^{3+/2+}$ and $\text{Fc}^{+/0}$, show a shift towards the negative direction. Moreover, it can be noticed that the dependence of E_f on c_S for ferrocene is weaker compared to the one for the other two redox couples. A careful experimental design using the procedures reported in reference³⁵ was essential to minimize spurious effects. In this way, the observed dependence of E_f on c_S genuinely shows the role of the non-ideality of the supporting electrolyte on the chemical potentials.

The order of magnitude of the observed dependence is in agreement with the Debye-Hückel theory^{36,37}; however, our conditions are outside the range of validity of this theory. The comparison

with more advanced theories such as the TCPC and Pitzer models^{13,14} could be more quantitative but it is not easy, because i) the necessary empirical parameters are not available for our ions and ii) they predict variation of the overall salt chemical potential, but cannot be used to determine the variation of the chemical potential of the single ions. Moreover, these theories only predict the thermodynamic equilibrium behaviour, which is outside the scope of this work. We thus modelled the electrostatic interaction as a complexation (like in the description of ion pairs), which can be extended to the kinetics of the electron-transfer process. The model is discussed below.

3.3 Dependence of the charge transfer resistance on the supporting electrolyte concentration

The values of R_{ct} as a function of the electrode potential for the three redox species at various concentrations of the supporting electrolyte (see S10 of SI), obtained from the fitting of the dynamic impedance spectra, can be used to extract information on the kinetics of the electron transfer reaction. The value of R_{ct} reaches a minimum at E_{ip} , as expected from the theory (see S11 of the SI). We called this minimum value of the charge transfer resistance $R_{ct,ip}$, which is related to the reaction rate constant of the electron transfer process by the following formula:

$$k = \frac{2RT}{(nF)^2 R_{ct,ip}} \frac{(D_{red})^{(1-\alpha)} (D_{ox})^\alpha}{c_{red,b} D_{red} + c_{ox,b} D_{ox}} \quad (2)$$

where $c_{red,b}$ and $c_{ox,b}$ are the bulk concentration of the redox species, and α is the charge transfer coefficient. Eq. (2) was obtained taking into account the change of the surface concentration of the redox species with the polarization of the electrode. This was used to calculate the reaction constant, k , from the measured value of $R_{ct,ip}$. The resulting values of k are shown in Fig. 3. We evaluated the error on k through the propagation of the error on R_{ct} , calculated according to reference.³⁸ It can be observed that the value of k increases with increasing concentration of supporting electrolyte, *independently* of the charge and nature of the redox species. This appears to be a common behaviour in this regime and is similar to what has been observed for other redox species.^{19,20,39}

According to the Frumkin effect⁴⁰, the predicted trend should be the inverse for $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-/4-}$ and $[\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_6]^{3+/2+}$. Considering that the point of zero charge for platinum is approximately -100 mV with respect to Ag/AgCl 3 M⁴¹, both redox couples are studied in the attractive regime: $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$

$/4^-$ is negative and is studied at an electrode potential that is higher than the potential of zero charge, while $[\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_6]^{3+/2+}$ is positive and is studied at an electrode potential that is lower than the potential of zero charge. Based on the Frumkin theory of the double layer, the reaction rate constant, k is expected to decrease with concentration, a trend that contrasts with our findings. For the $\text{Fc}^{+/0}$ redox couple, the anticipated outcome due to the Frumkin effect is a slight elevation in the reaction rate. These deviations from expectations based on the Frumkin effect can be compared with Ref.²² A graph of the apparent reaction rates, corrected for the Frumkin effect, is shown in S12 of the SI.

We propose that the relationship between E_f and k with respect to c_s , representing a thermodynamic and a kinetic parameter, respectively, can be concurrently explained by a single phenomenon. This phenomenon pertains to the non-ideal characteristics of the solution, which we have represented through the process of complexation. Interestingly, a similar model utilizing these concepts was recently put forward in Ref.^{42,43}

3.4 Modelling of the observed behavior in terms of ion pair formation

While there are thermodynamic theories able to model the non-ideal effects seen in Fig. 2, the thermodynamic parameters, such as the chemical potential or the activity coefficient, do not determine the kinetics; a more detailed (microscopic or mesoscopic) modelling is needed.⁴⁴

In order to model the effect of the supporting electrolyte on the thermodynamics and kinetics of the electron transfer from/to the redox couples, we model the electrostatic interaction between two ions as a complexation, like in the modelling of ion pairs (see Fig. 4). We consider ion pair formation as a complexation of the redox active species with a counter-ion, i.e., an ion of opposite charge belonging to the supporting electrolyte:

where O and R are the oxidized and reduced species, respectively, OC and RC are the complexes, and C is the counter-ion. The reaction constants of the two equilibria are K_{ox} and K_{red} , respectively.

We consider only one stage of complexation, although, in principle, a highly charged ion can go through multiple stages.

Fig. 4 shows the various possible routes of the electrochemical reaction. Each reaction route is represented by a pair (m, m') : they express the number of ion pairing in the oxidized and in the reduced form, respectively. The same pair (m, m') also appears as subscripts of the route reaction rates, $k_{m, m'}$, for the corresponding electrochemical reaction route. The routes 0,0 and 1,1 represent the charge transfer involving only free or only paired species, respectively:

In the case of the routes with reaction rates $k_{0,1}$ and $k_{1,0}$, the charge transfer takes place simultaneously with the association or dissociation of the ion pair:

The quantitative model is explained in details in section S13 of the SI. The most significant assumption here is that the ion pairing formation is always at equilibrium conditions (very fast). It is interesting to notice that the expression of the formal electrode potential as a function of c_S is *independent* of the electrochemical reaction routes, and that the reaction routes (0,1), (1,0), and (1,1) show the same expression of the reaction rate constant as a function of c_S .

The model is then used to obtain an expression for the formal electrode potential:

$$E_f = E^0 + \frac{RT}{F} \ln \left(\frac{1 + K_{\text{red}} c_S}{1 + K_{\text{ox}} c_S} \right) \quad (9)$$

and for the overall reaction rate constant, which takes into account all the reaction routes:

$$k = \frac{k_{0,0} + k_1 c_S}{(1 + K_{\text{ox}} c_S)^\alpha (1 + K_{\text{red}} c_S)^{(1-\alpha)}} \quad (10)$$

In these equations E^0 and $k_{0,0}$ are the standard equilibrium potential and reaction rate for the route (0,0), and k_1 is an effective reaction rate constant that accounts for the other routes (0,1), (1,0) and (1,1). In order to minimize the number of fitting parameters, α was fixed to 0.5, a value very close to the reported one.⁴⁵⁻⁴⁷ We fitted the experimental results on E_f and k (Figs. 2 and 3) with equation

9 and equation 10, respectively. The fitting parameters are E^0 , K_{red} , K_{ox} , $k_{0,0}$, and k_1 ; the same set was used for both equations.

The order of magnitude of the two complexation equilibrium constants K_{red} and K_{ox} is very different. K_{red} is the largest of the two constants for the redox couple $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-/4-}$ while K_{ox} is the largest for $\text{Fc}^{+/0}$ and $\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_6]^{3+/2+}$; this means that the mostly complexed form of a redox couple is the most charged, as can be expected by the electrostatic interaction. The smaller of the two equilibrium constants K_{red} and K_{ox} bears a large error and the statistical analysis suggested an over-parametrization, thus we decided to set it to 0 and remove it from the fit. The Eqs. (9-10), used for fitting, reduce to:

$$E_f = E^0 - \text{sgn}(z) \frac{RT}{F} \ln(1 + K_{\text{red/ox}} c_S) \quad (11)$$

$$k = \frac{k_{0,0} + k_1 c_S}{\sqrt{1 + K_{\text{ox/red}} c_S}} \quad (12)$$

where $\text{sgn}(z)$ is +1 or -1, for positively and negatively charged couples respectively, and $K_{\text{ox/red}}$ is the largest between K_{red} and K_{ox} .

Reliable values of E^0 , K_{ox} , $k_{0,0}$, and k_1 were obtained for $\text{Fc}^{+/0}$ and $\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_6]^{3+/2+}$. Instead, for the redox couple $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-/4-}$, some of the parameters have large errors and correlations, suggesting that an over-parametrization is still present. From the fit, we find $k_{0,0} \ll k_1 \cdot c_S$ and $K_{\text{red}} \cdot c_S \gg 1$; under these conditions, Eqs. (11-12) actually depend on only two parameters:

$$E_f = E' + \frac{RT}{F} \ln(c_S) \quad (13)$$

$$k = k' \sqrt{c_S} \quad (14)$$

where

$$E' = E^0 + \frac{RT}{F} \ln(K_{\text{red}}) \quad (15)$$

and

$$k' = \frac{k_1}{\sqrt{K_{\text{red}}}} \quad (16)$$

are the derived fit parameters. Using Eqs. (13-14), the derived parameters E' and k' can be reliably obtained by the fit, but they do not fully enable the evaluation of the initial set of parameters.

The results of the fitting (including errors) are reported in Table 1. The errors are below 20%. It is worth remarking that E' and k' are related to E^0 and k_1 through Eqs. (15-16), which depend on K_{red} , but this latter quantity is not quantitatively evaluated, although we know that it is large.

The different behavior of the redox couples is not only a mathematical formality derived from the statistical analysis, but it has a clear physical meaning in the frame of the model we have used for the fitting of the data.

Parameter	*[Fe(CN) ₆] ^{3-/4-}	**Ru(NH ₃) ₆ ^{3+/2+}	**Fc ⁺⁰
E' or E^0 / mV	251±2	-153±8	252.7±5
$\ln(K_{\text{ox}} / [\text{M}^{-1}])$	negligible	0.4±0.06	0.69±0.2
$\ln(K_{\text{red}} / [\text{M}^{-1}])$	large	negligible	negligible
$\ln(k_{0,0} / [\text{cm s}^{-1}])$	negligible	-1.4±0.05	-4.72±0.3
$\ln(k_1 \text{ or } k' / [\text{cm s}^{-1}])$	-1.07±0.02	-0.6±0.05	-1.97±0.1

*Eqs. (13-14) **Eqs. (11-12)

Table 1: Extracted fitting parameters according to the ion-pairing model. The terms "negligible" and "large" are quantitatively defined in the text, where Eqs. (11-14) are derived.

For the case of the redox couple [Fe(CN)₆]^{3-/4-}, we found that K_{ox} is very small and K_{red} very large. Physically, this means that the oxidized species form a negligible amount of ion pairs with the counter-ion (K^+ in this case), while almost all the reduced species exist only in the form of ion pairs. Namely, the species in solution are [Fe(CN)₆]³⁻ and K[Fe(CN)₆]³⁻. This implies that the electron-transfer does not occur between the free redox species, but follows rather the reaction route (0,1) (see Fig. 4). This explains why $k_{0,0}$ is negligible with respect to k_1 for this redox couple. For the case of Fc⁺⁰ and Ru(NH₃)₆^{3+/2+}, the ion pairing of reduced species is negligibly small. However, the ion pairing between the counter-ions (Cl^-) and oxidized species is not very large in the range of investigated concentrations of supporting electrolyte (see Table 1) and part of the oxidized form of the redox couple exist in its free form. For this reason, it is plausible that two

reaction paths are running in parallel, namely (0,0) and (1,0) (see Fig. 4), and $k_{0,0}$ has a measurable value, at variance with the case of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-/4-}$.

Our model can be combined with the Frumkin effect, and in particular in the S12 of SI the reaction rate constants corrected for the Frumkin effect and the corresponding fits are reported. The results are qualitatively similar to the ones reported above.

These results suggest that the electron-transfer reaction is probably not only a simple transfer of the electrons from / to the metal to / from the redox couple, but rather it can also involve the ion pairing with a counter-ion, even at concentrations of the supporting electrolyte as low as 0.3 M. In the redox couple $\text{Fc}^{+/0}$ this effect is less pronounced. This is understandable, as both redox species have low charge (0 and +1 respectively) and therefore appear to form very weak or even negligible ion pairs with the counter-ions. It is worth noting that the formation of the ion pairs has a very strong electrostatic nature rather than chemical. It is important also to stress that, although a simplification about the equilibrium condition of the ion pair process was made in order to calculate the value of k in the model, there is no evidence in the impedance spectra that this process is slow. In other words, these results suggest that a more realistic description of the electron-transfer reaction to the redox couples should be given by a *simultaneous electron and ion transfer*, i.e., reaction paths (1,0) or (0,1). If proven generally true, this finding will have a very strong impact on all the fields in which the electron transfer process is of paramount importance, including bio-electrochemistry, electro-catalysis, as well as heterogeneous catalysis, biochemistry, and biology.

4. Conclusions

The results obtained in this study underline that the electron-transfer reaction kinetics, even in simple case systems such as electrolyte solutions containing redox couples in contact with an inert electrode, is significantly altered in non-ideal conditions. The formal electrode potential and the reaction rate constant strongly depend on the concentration of the supporting electrolyte in the solution. While the former can be approximately modelled, even empirically and with some technical difficulties, by employing existing thermodynamic theories (Debye-Hückel, TCPC and

Pitzer models^{13,14}), the latter does not have an available treatment. For the first time, this has been investigated by studying three redox couples with very different characteristics, one of which is considered an ideal redox species. The analysis and the modeling show that the electron transfer occurs with a subsequent fast ion pairing with the counter-ion of the supporting electrolyte. This suggests that an accurate description of the electron transfer process should consider also a route of simultaneous electron and ion transfer. Moreover, if the observations made for the rate constant will be proven of general relevance for redox couples in concentrated electrolytes, the description of more complex electron-transfer reactions, such as the ones occurring in electrocatalysis and catalysis, bioelectrochemistry and biochemistry, electrochemical energy storage, and so on, should be revised.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

John Mugisa (Data curation: Lead; Formal analysis: Equal; Investigation: Lead; Software: Supporting; Writing original draft: Equal; Writing review & editing: Supporting)

Richard Chukwu (Data curation: Supporting; Formal analysis: Equal; Software: Lead)

Doriano Brogioli (Data curation: Supporting; Validation: Equal; Visualization: Lead; Writing original draft: Equal; Writing review & editing: Lead)

Fabio La Mantia (Conceptualization: Lead; Funding acquisition: Lead; Resources: Lead; Validation: Equal; Writing review & editing: Supporting)

Data availability

The datasets used and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on request.

References

- 1 Doblhofer, K. & Zhong, C. The mechanism of electrochemical charge - transfer reactions on conducting polymer films. *Synthetic Metals* **43**, 2865-2870, doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/0379-6779\(91\)91191-C](https://doi.org/10.1016/0379-6779(91)91191-C) (1991).
- 2 Schmickler, W. & Mohr, J. The rate of electrochemical electron-transfer reactions. *The Journal of chemical physics* **117**, 2867-2872 (2002).
- 3 Liu, T. *et al.* Improving Interfacial Electron Transfer via Tuning Work Function of Electrodes for Electrocatalysis: From Theory to Experiment. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* **123**, 28319-28326, doi:10.1021/acs.jpcc.9b09875 (2019).
- 4 Tyburski, R., Liu, T., Glover, S. D. & Hammarström, L. Proton-Coupled Electron Transfer Guidelines, Fair and Square. *Journal of the American Chemical Society* **143**, 560-576, doi:10.1021/jacs.0c09106 (2021).
- 5 Sawant, T. V., Yim, C. S., Henry, T. J., Miller, D. M. & McKone, J. R. Harnessing Interfacial Electron Transfer in Redox Flow Batteries. *Joule* **5**, 360-378, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joule.2020.11.022> (2021).
- 6 Zhang, J. *et al.* Interfacial electrochemical electron transfer in biology – Towards the level of the single molecule. *FEBS Letters* **586**, 526-535, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.febslet.2011.10.023> (2012).
- 7 Fukuzumi, S. & Hong, D. Homogeneous versus Heterogeneous Catalysts in Water Oxidation. *European Journal of Inorganic Chemistry* **2014**, 645-659, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/ejic.201300684> (2014).
- 8 Ahmad, M., Wolberg, A. & Kahwaji, C. I. in *StatPearls* (StatPearls Publishing, 2022).
- 9 Sjulstok, E., Olsen, J. M. H. & Solov'yov, I. A. Quantifying electron transfer reactions in biological systems: what interactions play the major role? *Scientific Reports* **5**, 18446, doi:10.1038/srep18446 (2015).
- 10 Elgrishi, N. *et al.* A practical beginner's guide to cyclic voltammetry. *Journal of chemical education* **95**, 197-206 (2018).
- 11 Tsierkezos, N. G. & Ritter, U. Influence of concentration of supporting electrolyte on electrochemistry of redox systems on multi-walled carbon nanotubes. *Physics and Chemistry of Liquids* **50**, 661-668 (2012).
- 12 Kontogeorgis, G. M., Maribo-Mogensen, B. & Thomsen, K. The Debye-Hückel theory and its importance in modeling electrolyte solutions. *Fluid Phase Equilibria* **462**, 130-152 (2018).
- 13 Ge, X., Wang, X., Zhang, M. & Seetharaman, S. Correlation and prediction of activity and osmotic coefficients of aqueous electrolytes at 298.15 K by the modified TCPC model. *Journal of Chemical & Engineering Data* **52**, 538-547 (2007).

- 14 Ge, X., Zhang, M., Guo, M. & Wang, X. Correlation and prediction of thermodynamic properties of some complex aqueous electrolytes by the modified three-characteristic-parameter correlation model. *Journal of Chemical & Engineering Data* **53**, 950-958 (2008).
- 15 Sipos, P. Application of the Specific Ion Interaction Theory (SIT) for the ionic products of aqueous electrolyte solutions of very high concentrations. *Journal of Molecular Liquids* **143**, 13-16 (2008).
- 16 Watkins, J. J. & White, H. S. The role of the electrical double layer and ion pairing on the electrochemical oxidation of hexachloroiridate(III) at Pt electrodes of nanometer dimensions. *Langmuir : the ACS journal of surfaces and colloids* **20**, 5474-5483, doi:10.1021/la0496993 (2004).
- 17 Qu, X. & Persson, K. A. Toward accurate modeling of the effect of ion-pair formation on solute redox potential. *Journal of Chemical Theory and Computation* **12**, 4501-4508 (2016).
- 18 Guo, S.-X. *et al.* Systematic Approach to the Quantitative Voltammetric Analysis of the Fe^{III}/Fe^{II} Component of the [α₂-Fe(OH)₂]₂P₂W₁₇O₆₁]-7-/8- Reduction Process in Buffered and Unbuffered Aqueous Media. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B* **109**, 20641-20651, doi:10.1021/jp0528459 (2005).
- 19 Beriet, C. & Pletcher, D. A microelectrode study of the mechanism and kinetics of the ferro/ferricyanide couple in aqueous media: The influence of the electrolyte and its concentration. *Journal of Electroanalytical Chemistry* **361**, 93-101 (1993).
- 20 Beriet, C. & Pletcher, D. A further microelectrode study of the influence of electrolyte concentration on the kinetics of redox couples. *Journal of Electroanalytical Chemistry* **375**, 213-218 (1994).
- 21 Leuaa, P., Priyadarshani, D., Choudhury, D., Maurya, R. & Neergat, M. Resolving charge-transfer and mass-transfer processes of VO²⁺/VO²⁺ redox species across the electrode/electrolyte interface using electrochemical impedance spectroscopy for vanadium redox flow battery. *RSC advances* **10**, 30887-30895 (2020).
- 22 Tsirlina, G. A. The role of supporting electrolyte in heterogeneous electron transfer. *Journal of Solid State Electrochemistry* **21**, 1833-1845 (2017).
- 23 Liu, Y. *et al.* Voltammetric Determination of the Reversible Potentials for [Ru₄O₄(OH)₂(H₂O)₄](γ-SiW₁₀O₃₆)₂]¹⁰⁻ over the pH Range of 2–12: Electrolyte Dependence and Implications for Water Oxidation Catalysis. *Inorganic Chemistry* **52**, 11986-11996, doi:10.1021/ic401748y (2013).
- 24 Andreu, R., Sanchez, F., Gonzelez-Arjona, D. & Rueda, M. The reduction of Cr(III) in concentrated aqueous electrolytes at a DME: The influence of anions. *Journal of Electroanalytical Chemistry and Interfacial Electrochemistry* **210**, 111-126, doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-0728\(86\)90317-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-0728(86)90317-7) (1986).
- 25 La Mantia, F. *Characterization of electrodes for lithium-ion batteries through electrochemical impedance spectroscopy and mass spectrometry*, ETH Zurich, (2008).
- 26 Battistel, A., Fan, M., Stojadinović, J. & La Mantia, F. Analysis and mitigation of the artefacts in electrochemical impedance spectroscopy due to three-electrode geometry. *Electrochimica Acta* **135**, 133-138, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2014.05.011> (2014).

- 27 Tran, A. T., Huet, F., Ngo, K. & Rousseau, P. Artefacts in electrochemical impedance measurement in electrolytic solutions due to the reference electrode. *Electrochimica Acta* **56**, 8034-8039, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2010.12.088> (2011).
- 28 Koster, D., Du, G., Battistel, A. & La Mantia, F. Dynamic impedance spectroscopy using dynamic multi-frequency analysis: A theoretical and experimental investigation. *Electrochimica Acta* **246**, 553-563 (2017).
- 29 Battistel, A., Du, G. & La Mantia, F. On the Analysis of Non-stationary Impedance Spectra. *Electroanalysis* **28**, 2346-2353 (2016).
- 30 Battistel, A. & La Mantia, F. On the physical definition of dynamic impedance: How to design an optimal strategy for data extraction. *Electrochimica Acta* **304**, 513-520 (2019).
- 31 Erinmwingbovo, C. & La Mantia, F. Estimation and correction of instrument artefacts in dynamic impedance spectra. *Scientific reports* **11**, 1-10 (2021).
- 32 Koster, D., Zeradhanin, A. R., Battistel, A. & La Mantia, F. Extracting the kinetic parameters of the hydrogen evolution reaction at Pt in acidic media by means of dynamic multi-frequency analysis. *Electrochimica Acta* **308**, 328-336 (2019).
- 33 Salman, M. M., Patzauer, M., Koster, D., La Mantia, F. & Krischer, K. Electro-oxidation of p-silicon in fluoride-containing electrolyte: a physical model for the regime of negative differential resistance. *The European Physical Journal Special Topics* **227**, 2641-2658 (2019).
- 34 Costa Santos, A., Sales, M. J. A. & Paterno, L. G. Electrochemical behaviour of some redox couples at layer-by-layer assembled poly(diallyl dimethylammonium)/reduced graphene oxide electrodes. *physica status solidi (a)* **214**, 1700096, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/pssa.201700096> (2017).
- 35 Chukwu, R., Mugisa, J., Brogioli, D. & La Mantia, F. Statistical Analysis of the Measurement Noise in Dynamic Impedance Spectra. *ChemElectroChem* **n/a**, e202200109, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/celec.202200109> (2022).
- 36 Sun, L., Lei, Q., Peng, B., Kontogeorgis, G. M. & Liang, X. An analysis of the parameters in the Debye-Hückel theory. *Fluid Phase Equilibria* **556**, 113398, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fluid.2022.113398> (2022).
- 37 Liu, J.-L. & Li, C.-L. A generalized Debye-Hückel theory of electrolyte solutions. *AIP Advances* **9**, 015214, doi:10.1063/1.5081863 (2019).
- 38 Taylor, J. R. *An Introduction to Error Analysis: The Study of Uncertainties in Physical Measurements*. (University Science Books, 1997).
- 39 Peter, L., Dürr, W., Bindra, P. & Gerischer, H. The influence of alkali metal cations on the rate of the Fe (CN) 64⁻/Fe (CN) 63⁻ electrode process. *Journal of Electroanalytical Chemistry and Interfacial Electrochemistry* **71**, 31-50 (1976).
- 40 Fawcett, W. R. Fifty years of studies of double layer effects in electrode kinetics—a personal view. *Journal of Solid State Electrochemistry* **15**, 1347-1358 (2011).
- 41 Gileadi, E., Argade, S. & Bockris, J. O. M. The potential of zero charge of platinum and its pH dependence. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry* **70**, 2044-2046 (1966).
- 42 Savéant, J.-M. Evidence for Concerted Pathways in Ion-Pairing Coupled Electron Transfers. *Journal of the American Chemical Society* **130**, 4732-4741, doi:10.1021/ja077480f (2008).

- 43 Savéant, J.-M. Effect of Ion Pairing on the Mechanism and Rate of Electron Transfer. Electrochemical Aspects. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B* **105**, 8995-9001, doi:10.1021/jp011374x (2001).
- 44 Brogioli, D. & La Mantia, F. Transition state theory in systems of interacting particles. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1812.07969* (2018).
- 45 Battistel, A., Petkovic, A. & La Mantia, F. Intermodulated non-linear analysis of a redox couple in solution. 2. Experimental results. *Electrochimica Acta* **176**, 1492-1499 (2015).
- 46 Xu, Q., Zhao, T. S., Wei, L., Zhang, C. & Zhou, X. L. Electrochemical characteristics and transport properties of Fe(II)/Fe(III) redox couple in a non-aqueous reline deep eutectic solvent. *Electrochimica Acta* **154**, 462-467, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2014.12.061> (2015).
- 47 Nam, J. H. Electrochemical Effectiveness Factors for Butler-Volmer Reaction Kinetics in Active Electrode Layers of Solid Oxide Fuel Cells. *Journal of Electrochemical Science and Technology* **8**, 344-355 (2017).

Figures

Fig 1: (a) Quasi-cyclic voltammetry with of a platinum microelectrode in contact with an aqueous solution containing 5 mM $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$ and 3 M KCl, acquired at a scan rate of 60 mV s^{-1} ; (b) three of the impedance spectra recorded at different voltages; (c) and (d) represent the charge transfer resistance R_{ct} , and the mass transport coefficient σ_{ct} , respectively.

Fig 2: Plot of formal potential, E_f vs. supporting electrolyte concentration. On the right scale the values of E_f for $[\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_6]^{3+/2+}$ is given, while the left one shows the values for $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-/4-}$ and $\text{Fc}^{+/0}$. The fits are represented by lines.

Figure 3: Plot of the reaction rate, k , vs. supporting electrolyte concentration. The fits are represented by lines.

Figure 4: Scheme illustrating possible reactions. *O* and *R* represent the oxidized and reduced free species, respectively, *C* is the counter ion, while *OC* and *RC* are complexed oxidized and reduced species, respectively. Double arrows \rightleftharpoons in black represent electrochemical reactions, with constants $k_{m,m'}$, while the blue double arrows \rightleftharpoons represent the ion pairing reactions, with equilibrium constant K_{ox} and K_{red} .